

Using Natural Language Understanding in a Recommender System to Match Resumes with Job Descriptions

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Real-world case study of applying classification (supervised) and clustering (unsupervised) techniques to power a recommender system. Highlight technical architecture and design decisions related to development of an industrial-strength, mission-critical, enterprise-grade production system that is deployed in the cloud.

2. Aim

To showcase application of Natural Language Understanding, predicated on innovative combination of supervised and unsupervised machine learning techniques, for matching resumes to job descriptions.

3. Material and methods

A leading Toronto-based startup, that is affiliated with MaRS, possessed corpora of approximately 200k resumes of high finance professionals as well as several thousand job descriptions pertaining to the finance sector. We used a variety of classification algorithms (binary, multiclass, multilable multioutput) in conjunction with myriad of clustering techniques (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency, Latent Dirichlet Allocation, and Latent Semantic Analysis) to tag these resumes and job descriptions.

4. Results

The tagged resumes and job descriptions powered a matching algorithm that recommended the top resume for a job description. This recommender system is performing at a high degree of correctness and is proposing relevant and pertinent matches among resumes and job descriptions.

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5. Conclusions

Advancements in Natural Language Understanding have unlocked a variety of valuable opportunities for design of Recommender Systems. Sophisticated classification and clustering techniques can be used within Recommender Systems. Planned next steps in this project include the use of Reinforcement Learning techniques to further improve quality of recommendations.

6. Keywords

Natural Language Understanding; Recommender System; Classification; Clustering

Author biography

Vik Pant Vik is a researcher and practitioner of applied machine learning, artificial intelligence, and neural networks. His scholarship and application are focused on the nexus of Science, Management, and Technology. For over a decade, he has studied and worked with various innovatory technologies including big data analytics and customer experience management. He advises startups in the areas of data science and reinforcement learning. His research focus is on conceptual modelling of strategic competition between organizations and systems. His academic research has been published in numerous peer-reviewed scholarly journals. He has also presented his academic research at juried scholarly conferences and workshops.